

The Cascades Game

Developed by: Centre for Systems Solutions

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Keywords

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Introduction

The Cascades Game is an interactive educational social-simulation game for university settings. It aims to foster systems thinking by introducing the concept of cascading climate impacts and the policy responses to address them. The game was developed in 2023 as part of the Project CASCADES (Cascading Climate Risks: Towards adaptive and resilient European Societies) and builds on their empirical research and policy models (CASCADES, n.d.). Simulating a global food crisis in 2028, players take on the roles of different global stakeholders and become members of the “European Task Force on global food supply”. Their goal is to develop recommendations for setting regulations to counter the global crisis. Therefore, they not only have to discuss, negotiate, and agree on solutions but must also react to the latest political, economic, and societal changes.

Facts

Release date:	28.03.2023
Developer:	Centre for Systems Solutions
Game type:	Hybrid
Number of players:	5–60
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	1.5–2 h
Languages:	English
Environment:	1–3 rooms, computer with stable Wi-Fi connection
Material:	printout materials from the game’s website, headsets, or speakers
Price:	available free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

While the Cascades Project received funding from the “European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program”, The Cascades Game itself has not acquired that much public attention yet. Although its educational effectiveness has not been empirically

investigated to date, the social simulation mechanisms it uses are widely considered valid and powerful (Remmer & Jernstedt, 1982). Furthermore, it can be emphasized that the cascading climate risks addressed in the game result from a multi-perspective and high-level real-world investigation (CASCADES, n.d.).

Game Principle & Process

Figure 1. Overview of cascading climate-related impacts and interconnected effects across policy, economy, and society in *The Cascades Game* (Centre for Systems Solutions). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

The game is a future-oriented social simulation that combines experiential learning, which involves learning through direct experience (Kolb, 2014), and social learning, a reflective process that happens when one shares their experiences, ideas, and environments with others (Dyball & Keen, 2012).

The game presents a complex challenge, shaped by uncertainty and ambiguity, that players must navigate with creativity, communication, and collaboration to understand interconnections and diverse perspectives (see Figure 1). The strategies players develop are constantly tested against external scenarios, which require flexible thinking and adaptation. The game is open-ended and has no specific goal. Its primary targets are the social, transformational, and reflective processes during play.

The game consists of two modules. It starts with the “Exploration Module,” a digital map that serves as an online multimedia introduction to a fictional yet plausible story of impact transmission, from the point of origin outside Europe to the very heart of the European Union. This is followed by the ‘Classroom Module,’ which constitutes the actual social simulation

workshop. The module begins with a simulated political summit focused on roleplaying and negotiating the global food crisis. Each player takes on the role of a country or organization and joins one of 3 working groups investigating the topic from different perspectives. The players and groups are provided with various media giving contextual information. Based on this information, the players develop, discuss, negotiate, and vote on policy proposals to counter the crisis. This is followed by a debriefing phase in which all three working groups present their voting results and reflect on the simulation experience. The debriefing can be supplemented with the conceptual framework for the cross-border impacts of climate change and can help bridge the gap between the simulation experience and the real world.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Taking on the different roles in the scenario and having multimedia materials provided, players are encouraged to actively engage in multiple behaviors, such as future-directed thinking and problem anticipation, taking and considering interdisciplinary perspectives, communicating and discussing interests and opinions, and finding compromises through collaboration. In addition to basic knowledge of the forms of cascading climate impacts and resource management skills, the game provides an opportunity to train in developing opinions and active policy responses that aim to inspire change and action in the real world. Furthermore, it fosters systems thinking, reflection on social situations, and insight into the dynamics of change. By doing so, it creates an inclusive space for developing future visions and allows players to understand key challenges along the way to their desired future.

The Cascades Game was designed for policy and climate educators as well as university teachers searching for an interactive introduction to cascading climate risks. The game targets adolescents and young adults and can be played during classes, workshops, or other initiatives that engage policymakers. Although the target group is not further specified, it is an advantage if players have some background knowledge of the main political, economic, and societal objectives beyond the game's input to better engage in discussions.

Although very detailed preparation materials for facilitators are provided, the game requires multiple hours of preparation time and 1-3 facilitators to create a summit atmosphere and guide participants through the simulation, as well as a reflective debriefing at the end.

All game and preparation materials can be accessed via the following link: <https://cascades.socialsimulations.org>.

Effectiveness

There are no purely empirical studies on the game. However, Weronika Adamczak & Lukasz Jarzabek (2023) note in their Handbook that multiple factors determine how effectively the game's learning objectives can be achieved.

The facilitator bears the demanding responsibility of guiding the storyline and discussions comprehensively.

The high-level multimedia materials are very engaging, create an immersive experience, and stand out from non-gamified teaching methods. However, students must be willing to get involved in their roles and the overall simulation, which is challenging because the complex storyline demands sustained concentration. Additionally, the debriefing process, designed to link the simulation experience and its content with the participants' real-world needs and practices, must be conducted with care and attention.

Nevertheless, through the broad range of skills that can be learned with social simulations (Remmer & Jernstedt, 1982), most players will have their own takeaways, including at least some of the main learning goals.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

In addition to the difficulties already mentioned, there are a few limitations to consider when choosing it for educational purposes.

Although the game developers specify a time horizon of 1.5–2 h, The Cascades Game can easily take longer depending on how deeply players dive into the discussions and reflect during the debriefing.

It might already be playable with 5 participants, but the feeling of an actual summit and the involvement of transdisciplinary perspectives are only achieved when more players participate.

Furthermore, the game presents a very Eurocentric perspective, depicting the European Union as the main executive body capable of solving the global food crisis.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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